

LIFE AND WORKS OF THE GREAT POET OYBEK

Turaeva N.

Student of the 2nd year of the group 8p-21
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry
Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

Valieva Z.

PhD, Associate Professor
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry
Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry
zulfiya-valieva-76@mail.ru
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7798481>

“No matter how big and how powerful the talent is, it is not on the surface, it is like a mine - it is in the depths of the earth. In order to mine this talent, one must first have a great mind, then great knowledge, perseverance, energy, and pain on top of that. Oybek, the owner of great talent, has all these qualities. With mentioned qualities, Oybek added great wealth to the spiritual treasure of our nation. The life of a writer is not measured by years, but by the results of creative activity. Oybek has not spent a single moment of his 40-year career, which is equivalent to 400 years, without success. In this respect, Oybek is portrayed as a master in front of the present and future literary generation.” - Abdulla Qahhar

Oybek began his career as a student, teaching language and literature in secondary schools, technical schools and labor faculties (1925-1927), National Economy, Agricultural and Pedagogical Institutes, and served as an assistant at the Faculty of Economics of the Tashkent Institute (1930-1935). Then, he worked as a researcher at the Scientific Research Institute of Cultural Construction (1933) and the Institute of Language and Literature under the Committee of Sciences (1934-1937). Soviet in 1937 the escalation of the state's repressive policy caused Oybek to be fired and harassed as a sympathizer of "nationalists" and "national believers". Oybek, who survived the repression due to coming from a poor family and being brought up in a boarding school, was hired as a translator-editor at the Educational and Pedagogical Publishing House of Uzbekistan only at the end of 1938. With the beginning of the 1941-1945 war, he was again persecuted as an undocumented person. With the establishment of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, the humanitarian department of the academy (1935-1951), and after the death of Hamid Olimjon, the board chairman of the Union of Writers of Uzbekistan, "Eastern Star" appointed editor-

in-chief of the magazine (1945-1959). He was the director of the Institute of Language and Literature (1950-1952) and the editor-in-chief of the magazine "Uzbek Language and Literature" (1958-1968). At the beginning of the 50s, with the beginning of another wave of repression, Oybek suffered a stroke and died as a result of a prolonged illness.

Oybek started his literary career as a poet. His first poem "The sound of an instrument" was published in 1922 in "Armugon" magazine. At this time, he was influenced by the poetry of Cholpon and the "young Ottomans" and published the collection "Feelings" (1926) and "Kongil naylari" (1929) containing poems inspired by them. In his early works, Oybek created free poems dedicated to the passing themes of the time, most of them were included in the collection "Mash'ala" (1932). Later, the poet paid great attention to the depiction of lyrical feelings and experiences and tried to create examples of "soul lyrics". His research in this area, especially an experience gained during the translation of the poetic novel "Eugene Onegin" (1936) and the influence of the lyricism of the works of Alexander Pushkin, gave good results. Oybek's poems, included in the "Chimyon Daftari" series, which capture the charming freshness and unique colors of Uzbek nature, became one of the royal examples not only of the poet's poetic work, but also of Uzbek lyrics in general. With these poems, the poet introduced a unique and elegant lyricism to Uzbek poetry, perfected the culture of describing delicate feelings and experiences, and polished the language of lyric poetry with subtle touches.

Oybek made a great contribution to the cultural development of the Uzbek people with his colorful creativity and his work as a great public figure. In 1980, the house-museum of Oybek was established in the house where the writer lived, and a statue was installed in it. A school, an avenue and one of the metro stations in Tashkent are named after Oybek, Termiz State University, collective farm in Tashkent region is named after Oybek. Oybek was posthumously awarded the Order of Merit (2001).

References:

1. Bat L., Koshchanov M., Aybek. Kritikobiografichesky essay, M., 1966; Yakubov H., Adib's mahrrat, T., 1966; Karimov N., Oybek, T., 1985; Karimov N., Buds made in Oybek gulshan, T., 1985.
2. Yakubov H. The skill of the writer. Tashkent , Ozadabiynashar, 1966.
3. Koshjanov M. Oybek skills. Tashkent , Ozadabiynashar, 1965.
4. Karimov N. Oybek. Tashkent . G. Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1985.
5. Saidnosirova Z. Oybegin is mine. T.: East, 1994.

